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FEATURES OF ESTABLISHING FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES WHEN ENTERING THE AMERICAN MARKET: PRACTICAL STEPS AND LEGAL NUANCES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the essential steps and legal nuances involved in establishing foreign economic activities in the USA market. It studies the current economic environment and analyzes effective market entry strategies, including joint ventures, partnerships, and subsidiaries. It explores regulatory requirements such as taxation, labor laws, and environmental regulations, and identifies potential business risks. It emphasizes the importance of understanding these aspects for successful operations in the complex and competitive American market.

Keywords: market entry, regulatory compliance, economic growth, foreign investment, risk management, legal frameworks, business strategies.

Introduction

Entering the American market constitutes a significant stage for numerous international enterprises due to its expansive consumer base, dynamic economic landscape, and high degree of innovation. As one of the largest economies globally, the USA offers considerable opportunities for business growth and expansion. However, successful navigation of this market necessitates a thorough understanding of both practical and legal dimensions.

The objective of this article is to provide an examination of the essential steps and legal nuances involved in establishing foreign economic activities within the American market. This study aims to elucidate the current economic environment, outline effective market entry strategies, detail the regulatory requirements, and

identify potential risks associated with operating in the USA.

Main part. Market analysis

The economic landscape of the USA is characterized by a resilient and diversified economy. In 2023, the USA economy has shown adaptability and growth despite global economic uncertainties. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth remains robust, driven by strong consumer spending, technological innovation, and a dynamic labor market. The unemployment rate has remained relatively low, fostering a conducive environment for business operations and expansion.

According to the USA Department of Commerce, Real GDP increased by 2,5% in 2023 compared to an increase of 1,9% in 2022 (fig.1).

Figure 1. GDP of the USA from 2017 to 2023, billion USA dollars

The growth was largely driven by an increase in income and spending among Americans. In 2023, the economy added 2,7 million jobs. Retail sales, excluding automobiles and gasoline, grew by 4,9%. Real personal income, adjusted for inflation, increased by 4,2% [1].

Key industries and sectors presenting substantial potential for foreign investment include technology, healthcare, renewable energy, and advanced manufacturing. The technology sector, in particular, continues to be a powerhouse of innovation, with significant investments in artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and biotechnology. Healthcare remains a critical area due to

the aging population and increasing demand for advanced medical services and pharmaceuticals. Renewable energy is another burgeoning sector, supported by federal and state policies aimed at reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainable energy sources [2]. Advanced manufacturing, leveraging advancements in automation and robotics, also presents lucrative opportunities for foreign investors.

Among these sectors, the import, wholesale, and distribution of confectionery products and food items stand out as especially promising. The USA food market, valued at over 1.5 trillion dollars in 2023, demonstrates strong demand for diverse and high-quality food

products [3]. The confectionery market, valued at approximately 44 billion dollars, exhibits steady growth, supported by innovative product offerings and increased consumer indulgence in premium sweets and snacks.

The robust infrastructure supporting the import and distribution sectors enhances their attractiveness. The USA possesses one of the most efficient and comprehensive logistics networks globally, facilitating smooth and timely distribution of goods. This infrastructure is critical for the food and confectionery sectors, where product freshness and shelf life are paramount.

Strategies for market entry

Entering the American market necessitates a strategic approach to ensure successful establishment and growth. Among the prevalent strategies for market entry are joint ventures, partnerships, and the establishment of subsidiaries. Each of these strategies offers distinct advantages and poses unique challenges, necessitating a careful evaluation based on specific business objectives, resource capabilities, and market conditions (table 1).

Table 1.

Strategy	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
Joint ventures	A collaborative agreement between foreign and domestic firms to create a new entity, leveraging mutual strengths	Access to local partner's market knowledge and distribution networks; shared investment risks and costs; enhanced competitive positioning	Potential conflicts of interest; shared control can limit decision-making autonomy; dependency on partner's performance
Partnerships	Various forms of strategic alliances, distribution agreements, or licensing arrangements	Leverages existing local infrastructure and expertise; lower capital investment; flexibility in market testing and gradual expansion	Requires clear contractual agreements; trust and alignment of goals are crucial; limited control over operations and brand image
Subsidiaries	Establishing a wholly-owned entity that operates independently under the control of the parent company	Complete control over operations and strategic direction; full ownership of profits; strong brand representation	High initial investment costs; compliance with complex local regulations; higher operational and managerial complexities

According to the author, the optimal market entry strategy for the American market depends on a thorough assessment of strategic objectives, resource capabilities, competitive landscape, regulatory environment, and cultural compatibility. By carefully evaluating these factors, businesses can select a strategy that aligns with their goals and maximizes their potential for success in the USA market.

Legal framework and regulatory requirements

Navigating the USA legal and regulatory environment is critical for foreign businesses aiming to establish operations in the American market. The USA possesses a complex and multifaceted legal system that encompasses federal, state, and local regulations. These regulations cover various aspects of business operations, including taxation, labor laws, environmental regulations, and intellectual property rights, all of which foreign entities must adhere to ensure compliance and avoid legal pitfalls.

Taxation is one of the most significant areas of concern. The USA operates a federal income tax system managed by the Internal Revenue Service (IRS), which requires businesses to file annual tax returns and comply with various tax obligations, including corporate income tax, payroll taxes, and sales taxes. The corporate tax rate for businesses in the USA is 21%. This rate applies to all taxable income of a corporation, both domestic and foreign-derived, if the corporation is based

in the USA [6]. The tax code also includes various deductions, credits, and other provisions that can impact the effective tax rate for businesses. According to the IRS corporate tax rates and compliance requirements can vary significantly, depending on the nature and structure of the business.

Labor laws in the USA are equally comprehensive, designed to protect the rights of workers and ensure fair labor practices. The Fair Labor Standards Act (FLSA) sets the minimum wage, overtime pay, and child labor standards. According to the USA Department of Labor, the federal minimum wage is 7,25 dollars per hour [7]. It is important to note that many states also have their own minimum wage laws, and in cases where an employee is subject to both state and federal minimum wage laws, the employee is entitled to the higher minimum wage. Additionally, businesses must comply with the Occupational Safety and Health Act (OSHA, which mandates workplace safety and health standards to prevent work-related injuries and illnesses. The Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) enforces laws against workplace discrimination, requiring businesses to adopt non-discriminatory hiring practices and maintain equitable workplace conditions.

Environmental regulations are enforced by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), which oversees compliance with laws such as the Clean Air Act and the

Clean Water Act. These regulations aim to minimize environmental impact and ensure sustainable business practices. Businesses involved in manufacturing, energy production, and other high-impact industries must obtain the necessary permits and comply with EPA standards to avoid substantial fines and legal actions.

Intellectual property rights (IPR) protection is another critical component of the USA regulatory environment. The USA Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) oversees the registration and protection of patents, trademarks, and copyrights. The robust legal framework for IPR is designed to protect innovations and creative works, encouraging investment in research and development [8]. Businesses must navigate the complexities of patent applications, trademark registrations, and copyright laws to safeguard their intellectual

assets. Infringement of IPR can result in significant legal consequences, including injunctions, damages, and loss of business reputation.

Compliance with these regulatory requirements necessitates a proactive and informed approach. Foreign businesses must invest in legal expertise to navigate the USA regulatory landscape effectively. This includes engaging with local legal counsel, understanding the intricacies of federal and state regulations, and maintaining up-to-date knowledge of regulatory changes.

Navigating business operations

Establishing a business entity in the USA necessitates selecting an appropriate legal structure, comprehending the registration process, and fulfilling regulatory requirements (table 2).

Table 2.

Legal structures

Legal structure	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
Sole proprietorship	Owned and operated by one individual; simplest form	Simple to establish and manage	Limited liability protection
Partnership	Owned by two or more individuals sharing profits and losses	Easy to form, shared resources	Joint liability, potential for conflicts
Limited Liability Company (LLC)	Hybrid structure offering limited liability protection with flexible management arrangements	Limited liability, flexible management	More paperwork, subject to taxes
Corporation	Separate legal entity owned by shareholders; can be publicly traded or privately held	Limited liability, ability to raise capital through stocks	Complex to establish, rigorous regulatory requirements

Import and export procedures in the USA are regulated by the Customs and Border Protection (CBP) agency. Businesses engaged in international trade must comply with stringent customs regulations, which encompass the classification of goods, valuation, and adherence to international trade agreements. Importers are required to file entry documents and pay duties, while exporters must comply with export control regulations overseen by the Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS) and the International Traffic in Arms Regulations (ITAR). Furthermore, businesses must stay informed about sanctions and embargoes affecting trade with specific countries.

Managing business risks in the USA entails a comprehensive approach involving the identification of potential risks, development of mitigation strategies, and implementation of insurance and legal safeguards. Foreign enterprises face various risks such as regulatory compliance, market volatility, and operational challenges. Effective risk management begins with thorough market research to understand the competitive landscape and regulatory environment.

A diversified investment strategy is crucial to minimizing exposure to market volatility. By spreading investments across different sectors and regions, businesses can protect themselves against sector-specific downturns and economic fluctuations [9]. Foreign enterprises should regularly review and update their risk management practices to adapt to changing market conditions and emerging risks.

Insurance plays a pivotal role in safeguarding businesses against unexpected events. General liability insurance covers legal claims arising from accidents or injuries on business premises, while property insurance protects against damage to physical assets from natural disasters, theft, or vandalism. Business interruption insurance provides coverage for lost income during periods when business operations are halted due to unforeseen circumstances, ensuring financial stability and continuity.

Business insurance in the USA features diverse coverage options tailored to various industries, including general liability, property, business interruption, workers' compensation, professional liability, commercial auto, and cyber liability insurance. Policies are highly customizable to meet specific business needs and comply with state regulations, which vary widely. Premiums are influenced by factors such as business size, industry risk, and claims history. Businesses often utilize bundled policies for cost efficiency, while state insurance departments oversee compliance to ensure protection and fairness for both insurers and policyholders.

Conclusion

Successfully entering the American market requires a comprehensive understanding of the economic landscape, strategic market entry approaches, regulatory frameworks, business operations, and risk management. The USA presents substantial opportunities for growth due to its robust economy, diverse consumer base, and innovative industries. Effective market entry

strategies such as joint ventures, partnerships, and subsidiaries must be selected based on thorough evaluations of business objectives and market conditions. Navigating the intricate regulatory environment necessitates compliance with federal, state, and local laws, while robust risk management practices, including insurance and legal safeguards, are essential for mitigating potential business risks. By adhering to these strategic and regulatory guidelines, foreign enterprises can achieve sustainable growth and long-term success in the highly competitive American market.

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